

Decomposition of Potassium Ferrocyanide in Presence of Mercury(II)-Thiourea Complex*

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Mercury(II)-thiourea complex is found to act as catalyst in the decomposition of potassium ferrocyanide at low pH to produce Prussian Blue. The mechanism of decomposition has been suggested and discussed.

POTASSIUM ferrocyanide hydrolyses in presence of metal ions which have affinity towards cyanide ions¹ to give $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5(\text{OH}_2)]^{3-}$. In presence of certain catalysts², the reaction proceeds further to produce colloidal solution of Prussian Blue, $\text{KFe}(\text{III})[\text{Fe}(\text{II})(\text{CN})_6]$. Thus, thiourea (T) complex of gold(I) is found to act as catalyst³ in the decomposition of ferrocyanide ion to give Prussian Blue. Our investigation⁴ on the reaction of certain S-ligated class b metal⁵ complexes with potassium ferrocyanide has shown that these complexes catalyze the decomposition of potassium ferrocyanide and produce Prussian Blue. This paper deals with the probable decomposition of ferrocyanide ion in presence of $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ -T complex and the formation of Prussian Blue.

Experimental

The mechanism of decomposition of ferrocyanide ion in presence of $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ -T complex was followed by measuring optical density of solutions with time using a Metrohm Herisau Spectrocolorimeter, Model E1009, at 660 nm wavelength. (The maximum light absorption of Prussian Blue solution is at 660 nm with a molar extinction coefficient of 4200^3). The experimental techniques were the same as described by an earlier paper³. Precautions were taken to avoid photochemical decomposition⁶ of the ferrocyanide ion by screening the solutions from intense light.

To observe the relation between the rate of reaction and concentration of reactants, optical density at various time intervals of solutions containing different concentrations of HgCl_2 , T, and $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ at different pH was recorded. The pH of the solutions were controlled by using a pH meter with a glass electrode. Perchloric acid was used to obtain a definite acidity.

Results and Discussions

Fig. 1 shows the optical density at different time intervals of various pH solutions containing constant

concentrations of HgCl_2 , T, and $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$. The graph shows that the rate of decomposition of potassium ferrocyanide increases with decrease in pH.

Fig. 1. Decomposition of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ at different pH: (1) 5.0, (2) 4.5, (3) 4.0, (4) 3.5, (5) 3.0, (6) 2.8, (7) 2.5. Concentrations of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$, 1×10^{-3} , T, 2×10^{-3} , HgCl_2 , $2 \times 10^{-5} M$.

Fig. 2 shows the relation between the rate of decomposition of ferrocyanide and concentration of

Fig. 2. Decomposition of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ at pH 2.8 and HgCl_2 concentration (1) 5×10^{-6} , (2) 8×10^{-6} , (3) 1×10^{-5} , (4) 2×10^{-5} , (5) 5×10^{-5} , (6) 1×10^{-4} , (7) $2 \times 10^{-4} M$. Concentrations of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$, 1×10^{-3} , T, $2 \times 10^{-3} M$.

* Work carried out at Anorg. Chem. Institut, Göttingen.

HgCl₂ at constant pH of 2.8 and constant concentrations of K₄Fe(CN)₆ and T. It is clear from the figure that the rate of decomposition is remarkable as the concentration of Hg²⁺ ion increases. Fig. 3 deals with the rate of reaction at pH 2.8, and concentrations of HgCl₂ and K₄Fe(CN)₆ are 2 × 10⁻⁵

Fig. 3. Decomposition of [Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻ at pH 2.8 and T concentration (1) 1 × 10⁻⁴, (2) 5 × 10⁻⁴, (3) 1 × 10⁻³, (4) 2 × 10⁻³, (5) 1 × 10⁻², (6) 2 × 10⁻² M. Concentrations of HgCl₂, 2 × 10⁻⁵, [Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻, 1 × 10⁻³ M.

and 1 × 10⁻³ M respectively. Thiourea concentration is being varied from 1 × 10⁻⁴ to 2 × 10⁻² M. Fig. 4 relates the rate of decomposition at pH 2.8 and concentrations of Hg²⁺ and T are 5 × 10⁻³ and 2 × 10⁻³ M respectively. The concentrations of [Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻ is being varied from 5 × 10⁻⁵ and 5 × 10⁻³ M

Fig. 4. Decomposition of [Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻ at pH 2.8 and its concentration (1) 5 × 10⁻⁵, (2) 1 × 10⁻⁴, (3) 5 × 10⁻⁴, (4) 1 × 10⁻³, (5) 3 × 10⁻³, (6) 5 × 10⁻³ M. Concentrations of HgCl₂, 2 × 10⁻⁵ and T, 2 × 10⁻³ M.

One can derive from Fig. 3 that at very low concentration of T, the rate of decomposition of [Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻ is quite negligible. A blank experiment without T has also shown similar observations.

Hg²⁺ is known to form different molecular complexes⁷⁻⁸ with T. As HgCl₂ alone does not bring the formation of Prussian Blue from K₄Fe(CN)₆ and the reaction is facilitated by the addition of T, it is quite reasonable to postulate that Hg(II)-T complex catalyses the decomposition of [Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻. By varying the concentrations of one of the reactants at a time and keeping the concentrations of all other species constant and by measuring the initial rates of the reactions, the order of the reaction with respect to [H⁺], [Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻ and [Hg-T] complex was

TABLE 1. A REPRESENTATIVE SET OF CALCULATED ORDER WITH RESPECT TO VARIOUS CONSTITUENTS FROM INITIAL RATE.

[H ⁺] g. ions.l ⁻¹	[Fe(CN) ₆] ⁴⁻ M	[Hg-T] [*] M	Initial rate	Order
3.16 × 10 ⁻³	1 × 10 ⁻³	2 × 10 ⁻³	6.67 × 10 ⁻³	1.02 ^a
1.58 × 10 ⁻³	1 × 10 ⁻³	2 × 10 ⁻³	4.17 × 10 ⁻³	
1.58 × 10 ⁻³	1 × 10 ⁻³	2 × 10 ⁻⁴	5.00 × 10 ⁻³	1.02 ^b
1.58 × 10 ⁻³	1 × 10 ⁻³	5 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.13 × 10 ⁻³	
1.58 × 10 ⁻³	1 × 10 ⁻³	2 × 10 ⁻⁵	6.25 × 10 ⁻³	0.97 ^c
1.58 × 10 ⁻³	1 × 10 ⁻³	2 × 10 ⁻⁵	4.00 × 10 ⁻³	

* As the concentration of T taken is always in excess, it is presumed that all the Hg²⁺ taken is in the form of Hg-T complex.

- a = with respect [H⁺]
- b = with respect [Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻
- c = with respect [Hg-T].

established to be equal to unity. The data on the initial rates of the reactions calculated from Figs. 1 to 3 are summarized in Table 1. However, in the case of the determination of the order of the reaction with respect to ferrocyanide the initial rate method was not satisfactory and a plot of log O.D. against time was made (from Fig. 4) and found to be linear indicating that this is also first order with respect to [Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻. On the basis of the observed order with respect to various species and assuming that Hg-T complex is the catalysing species the following mechanism is postulated :

Reaction (2) is supported by the supposition that oppositely charged species will try to combine and further by the isolation⁹ of a yellow sparingly soluble mixed complex [(Hg.T₃)₂Fe(CN)₆]. It is also observed that this mixed complex at low pH in presence of potassium ferrocyanide, gives Prussian Blue¹⁰.

The rate law may be derived for the reaction scheme as :

$$\frac{-d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}}{dt} = k[\text{HgT}_x\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{2-}][\text{H}_3\text{O}^+] \quad \dots (4)$$

where k is the rate coefficient for the rate determining step. For the rapid equilibrium for the formation of the mixed complex $[\text{HgT}_x\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{2-}$, the equilibrium constant,

$$K = \frac{[\text{HgT}_x\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{2-}}{[\text{HgT}_x]^{2+}[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}} \quad \dots (5)$$

Substituting this for the concentration of the mixed complex in equation (4), the rate expression is written as :

$$\frac{-d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}}{dt} = kK[\text{HgT}_x]^{2+}[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}[\text{H}_3\text{O}^+] \quad \dots (6)$$

The regenerated Hg(II)-T complex combines again either with $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ or with $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5(\text{OH})_2]^{3-}$ species to give mixed complex, which further breaks down and another cyanide ion is stripped off from the coordination sphere of Fe^{2+} . Thus, the cycle of reaction goes on until all the cyanide ions have been replaced from the coordination site of Fe^{2+} . Once Fe^{2+} is formed in solution which is readily oxidized by the dissolved oxygen of the air to give Fe^{3+} , Fe^{3+} ion combines with the excess of ferrocyanide present in solution to produce Prussian Blue. The last phase of the reaction is

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